

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

CRIRES, after the upgrade
Jonathan Smoker

Goto: I would like higher accuracy in pixel scale. As we know the distance to a star [is known] with better accuracy by recent astrometry mission. We do not want to be limited by the accuracy of the pixel scale.

We will try and measure this better on-sky in CRIRES plus by looking at stars with very well known positions. This will be easier now with GAIA. Of course there will likely be optical distortion to take into account. I do not know how well the pixel scale on the new detectors will be known or if it can be measured in the lab beforehand or to what accuracy.

Osip: Regarding the split repeatability problem, what was the mechanism? how were positions of blades defined? was the system tested warm and verified? was this an effect of cold cycling? We are considering a future instrument with the use of variable slit width capabilities, so what can we test in advance to help resolve issues?

I don't know the answer to this. I suggest you get in touch with Ulli Kaeufl <hukauf1@eso.org>

Bristow: Comments: Pixel scale for CRIRES+ is 2/3 of oCRIRES for the science Focal Plane Array, 8/15 of oCRIRES for the Slit Viewer camera due to a change in focal length. Persistence is being carefully characterised for CRIRES+ detectors. We will run as cold as possible to minimize persistence, but we will still expect to have to be careful with exposure times for each lamp in each setting.